

PSYCHOCORRECTIVE METHODS OF FORMING A RELATIONSHIP WITH CONFLICT TEENAGERS IN THE WORK OF A SCHOOL PSYCHOLOGIST

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Anontatsiya: *In this article, the changes observed in the psychology of adolescence are studied by a school psychologist, and several methods of psychocorrective approach to teenagers in conflict situations are mentioned.*

Key words: *adolescent, psychocorrection, conflict, tension, vagrancy, psychoprophylaxis, behavior.*

The question of the effectiveness of the school psychologist's psychocorrective activity in the context of interpersonal conflicts among teenagers is one of the most complex issues, and the evaluation of the effectiveness of psychocorrection requires a clear definition of its methods. The most important thing when considering this aspect of the problem is that in practical work, usually a combination of several methods is used simultaneously. In this case, the method in psychocorrection can be expressed by itself only as a method of achieving the psychocorrective goal in a general way.

And finally, evaluating the effectiveness of the methods used for psychocorrection is complicated by the fact that the same method can give different results when used by different specialists. In this case, not only the level of their professional qualifications, but also their personal qualities are important in the characteristics of specialists. As part of the conditions for the effectiveness of psychocorrective work, such various conditions are studied that compliance with them increases the effectiveness of psychocorrection in general. It should be noted that there are many different conditions of effectiveness in the literature for various forms and methods of correction carried out in connection with concrete psychocorrective issues.

Another approach to evaluating the effectiveness of psychocorrective work presented in the literature is related to the development of quantitative indicators of changes in the behavior of participants of psychological correction.

Thus, the question of the effectiveness of the school psychologist's psychocorrective activities in the context of interpersonal conflicts among teenagers can be considered from different perspectives.

Before moving on to express the qualitative criteria of the psychocorrective activity of the school psychologist in the conditions of interpersonal conflict among teenagers, it is permissible to point out the difficulties that arise in the definition of such criteria.

The main thing that makes it difficult to evaluate the effectiveness of psychocorrective work is the lack of normativeness in psychological correction.

One of the factors that make it difficult to evaluate the effectiveness of psychocorrective work in conflict situations is that the correction itself is not aimed at the conflict or its quick resolution, but primarily at ensuring the personal development of the participants in the conflict. However, the principle of "personal achievement" is decisive here.

In assessing the effectiveness of psychocorrective activity, the factor of delay of results is also important, because it is known that in the case of effectively conducted psychological correction, the highest results are achieved only after 6-7 months after the end of the exposure.

Thus, we can understand that the criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of correctional work in conflict situations are not limited to statistical indicators of the frequency of conflicts, conflict resolution and relationship resolution. It is necessary to check the results of the correction, which show the stability of the changes that occurred during the correction process, after the process is finished.

Work experiences on prevention and coping with interpersonal conflicts among teenagers show that a real school conflict can be analyzed at several levels.

A) from the point of view of the objective characteristics of the organization of the educational process in the school;

B) socio-psychological characteristics of the class, from the point of view of concrete interpersonal relations between the participants;

V) in terms of age, gender, individual-psychological and personality characteristics of the participants;¹

Therefore, in developing the criteria for the effectiveness of the school psychologist's correctional activities in the context of interpersonal conflicts among teenagers, we proceed from the following requirements that must be met:

1. To maximally reflect the dynamics of factors causing conflicts of different nature, to characterize the individual psychological characteristics of the

¹ Варга, А.Я. Психологическая коррекция нарушений общения младших школьников в игровой группе / А.Я. Варга // Семья в психологической консультации. - М., 1989. - С. 101-107.

participants of the psychocorrective process and to change the level of their social adaptation.

2. The criteria should make it possible to assess the effectiveness of psychocorrective work both from the point of view of the objective dynamics of the factors causing the conflict, and from the point of view of the participants of the psychocorrective process.

Criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of psychocorrective work should be sufficiently independent from each other.

To do this, methods of researching the effectiveness of psychocorrective work should allow obtaining numerical indicators of the considered criteria, recording the changes that occur in the process of psychocorrection, and statistical analysis of the results obtained with their help.

The study of the dynamics of conflict-causing factors, which are important in terms of the occurrence of interpersonal conflicts among adolescents in the educational process, based on the results of psychocorrective measures, indicates positive changes in them, at the same time, a positive answer to the question of the effectiveness of such work.

Research of the effectiveness of psychocorrective work carried out in different ways made it possible to distinguish several groups of adolescents and class groups according to the results of psychocorrective work.

Analyzing the effectiveness of psychocorrective work organized in the form of joint activities of teenagers using objective methods of efficiency assessment made it possible to distinguish two groups of school classes:

1. Classes with significant dynamics of conflict-causing factors of different nature (40% of the checked classes);
2. Classes with insignificant dynamics of conflict-causing factors of different nature (60% of the checked classes);

However, analysis of self-reports of students in both groups yielded almost identical results. "Has your classroom become harmonious and enjoyable for you?" 88% of the students in the first group and 79% of the students in the second group gave a positive answer to the question.²

Questionnaires conducted among teachers working in schools where psychocorrective work was carried out showed that in the first and second cases, regardless of the indicators of the dynamics of conflict-causing factors determined

² Осипова, А.А. Общая психокоррекция: Учебное пособие / А.А. Осипова. - М.: ТЦ Сфера, 2002. - 512 с.

according to the results of objective methods, the conflict behavior of the observed adolescents decreased (73 percent and 46 percent).

The scale for evaluating the effectiveness of psychocorrective work developed by us showed that the effectiveness of correction in the first group of school classes differed statistically significantly from the effectiveness of correction conducted in the second group of classes according to the first, second and third criteria, and no significant differences were observed according to the fourth and fifth criteria.

Analysis of the effectiveness of psychocorrective work in the form of group correctional training made it possible to distinguish three groups of teenagers. The first group included adolescents with significant dynamics of personality and socio-psychological conflict-causing factors (statistically significant changes). Teenagers with such indicators made up 61 percent. The second group included adolescents with insignificant dynamics of personality and socio-psychological factors causing conflict (27.5% of the total number of participants in group training). According to the results of psychodiagnostic methods, adolescents without the dynamics of conflict-causing factors were included in the third group (11.5 percent).

All three groups showed an increase in self-reported satisfaction with their social situation (97% in the first group, 85% in the second and 62% in the third group). Almost all the participants of group training noted that they "began to better understand themselves and the people around them."

Teachers who work with teenagers who participated in group trainings mentioned that the tendency to conflict and aggression in these teenagers has decreased.

The use of the psychocorrective work performance assessment scale showed statistically significant dynamics of conflict-causing factors in the first group of adolescents according to the third, fourth and fifth criteria. In the second group of teenagers, statistically significant dynamics were observed according to the sixth criterion. In the third group, no significant dynamics of conflict-causing factors were observed.

The assessment of the effectiveness of the psychocorrective work carried out in the form of the participation of the school psychologist as a mediator in interpersonal conflicts made it possible to see statistically significant dynamics in the sixth criterion of the efficiency scale. No statistically significant dynamics were observed according to the fifth criterion.

Thus, the analysis of the results shows that different forms and methods of organizing psychocorrective work have different effectiveness of psychocorrective influence on conflict-causing factors of different nature.

At the same time, it is clear that the simultaneous use of various forms of psychocorrective work allows to achieve a significant correctional result, because it can have a corrective effect on almost all conflict-causing factors.

The last case once again indicates the need to organize the psychocorrective work of the school psychologist in the situation of interpersonal conflicts among teenagers on the basis of a systematic, comprehensive approach.

Above, we talked about the need for late diagnosis of psychocorrective results. The psychodiagnostic examination of the participants of the psychocorrection group conducted three months after the psychocorrection made it possible to note the positive dynamics of personality and social-psychological factors causing conflicts, although not statistically significant. Similar results were obtained in a re-examination of interpersonal conflict participants, in which the psychologist played the role of mediator.

We proceed from the idea that the general psychological model of activity is logically a model of individual activity. At the same time, psychocorrective activity is a joint activity organized according to the rules of interpersonal interaction and behavior.

In this regard, we suggest that a) general psychological (individual and joint activity) and special (including transactional analysis) methods can be used in the design and analysis of the psychocorrective model; b) their selection and application is determined by the research task and its basic paradigm in a specific case; c) it can be noted that research in this field still has wide prospects.

10. A psychocorrective approach to overcoming and preventing conflicts in adolescents involves introducing them into a specially organized system of relations, which forms an objective source for optimizing the process of personality development, develops various forms of subjectivity, an arsenal of non-conflictual manifestations of behavior, and the skills of constructive resolution of interpersonal conflicts expands, creates conditions for critical evaluation of one's own behavior, reconsideration of attitude towards other people and oneself.

The potential of a psychologist's mediating activity is also seen in our work in the practical work of child and juvenile inspectors.

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